

IMPROVED AWARENESS OF ARCHITECTURAL CONSULTANTS TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF TELECOM - COMPATIBLE BUILDINGS

Ikechukwu Obiora Okereke & K.E .Chukwujindu

Department of Architecture, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

io.okereke@unizik.edu.ng

Abstract

The ability to interconnect and communicate wirelessly in and around the built environment with sufficient aptitude is becoming progressively important as the array of consumer-grade portable devices with broadband wireless functionality flourishes. These devices provide incredible functionality, much of which is dependent on broadband internet connectivity which, from a user perspective, is frequently sub-optimal. With almost a hundred percent of today's communication and data consumption happening within the domain of wireless technology, it is surprising that for the built environment in Nigeria, codes/guidelines do not yet exist in the building industry to guide and enhance their deployment and use within our built environment. The knowledge to limit, or eliminate and enhance these wireless waves as needed through spatial and material manipulations is virtually non-existent amongst our built environment practitioners. Design solutions and developments are all of the time made without recourse to the proper placement of communication infrastructure, educated use of building materials and spatial organization. This paper provides a structural guideline or formwork for the creation of codes of practice and conduct with the purpose of optimizing wireless communication in our built environment. It concludes that for wireless systems, the learned ability to compensate for the dynamics of radio propagation within the built environment is crucial for achieving optimal performance.

Key words: Building codes, built environment, optimization, wireless, communication.

Introduction

Advances in wireless technology has ushered in a gamut of telecommunication services never before known to humanity. These use radio waves essentially as the medium of communication. After commercial land line long distance telephone service was established, a horde of other telecommunications technologies were also adapted. These included mobile satellite phones, satellite television, satellite radio and satellite internet access. The era of the computer networks and the internet actually started as far back as 1940, However it was not until the 1960s that researchers started to investigate packet switching — a technology that would allow chunks of data to be sent to different computers without first passing through a central mainframe. The late 1970s saw the proliferation of various computer to computer communication ordinances (protocols) and by the late 80's and 90's, most of the developed world and the pertinent stake holders in the global communication business had started to finalize and agree on the standard protocols and procedures which the internet and other industries it supports heavily such as telecommunications today utilize.

Nigeria, as a developing country, took advantage of this novel industry and quickly jettisoned land line or copper based communication infrastructure. As of December 2017, Nigeria had a population of around 180million people and a combined subscriber base of 241,331,543(connected lines) and an active base of 145,059,514 (NCC 2018).

Fig 1: Building Automation / Networking. Source: ORing Industrial Networking Corp.

Figure 1 reveals in clear terms the interconnectivity between electronic gadgets used at different floors within the same building. The new focus of wireless communication is shifting from voice to multimedia services. User requirements are moving from fundamental technology to the simply reliable and cost effective wireless communication systems that is supported by most mobile devices across the globe. Furthermore, every aspect of our lives as human beings is now been influenced by this wireless technology. It will not be wrong to assume we spend almost 85% of our lives in one form of designed environment or the other. Whether at our schools, places of worship, market places, workplaces, entertainment and leisure arenas, we are increasingly dependent on the availability, performance and functionality of the wireless medium and infrastructure.

It is therefore the responsibility of the Architect to understand the different variations and permutations of the components of the built environment and the various ways they interact with the propagation of wireless waves. For an example; In some spaces in our built environment, it may be desired that there should be no penetration of electromagnetic waves which is a principal mode of data transference for wireless technology, yet it floods there while in some other area, a healthy presence of these signals may be needed for educational or other purposes and yet the space is not designed to optimize the signal entry.

The availability and strength of electromagnetic waves, which is the spine of wireless communication, is appreciably affected by the spatial and material characteristics of the built environment near and around its path as much as the human activities within built interior spaces is affected by the availability and strength of electromagnetic waves entering such spaces. As architects we are more concerned with the later situation.

With the greater portion of our lives: information, banking, entertainment, etc. dependent on the internet (today delivered wirelessly, completely enabled by electro-

magnetic waves) and because of the huge lacuna in the body of knowledge about the nature of these interactions, architectural design decisions are made without recourse to this all important aspect of our spaces thus leading to undesirable penetration and poor signal reception within certain spaces or areas of a building.

In summary, this translates to these basic problems:

- Poor and erratic wireless network reception in certain parts of the built environment
- Electromagnetic interference in areas which the client may for whichever reason, desire none whatsoever.
- Poor arrangement / placement of macro and micro-communication infrastructure.

Awareness needs to be raised in the construction industry about this issue and a debate started about the implications for the Connected /Smart Home agenda which are likely to require the increased use of wireless products to achieve effective management, as well as addressing other industries such as communications, entertainment and tele-health for example. *Rudd (2014)*.

Aim of this Study

The aim of this work is to raise the awareness of the Nigerian Architect or built industry practitioner on the subject of wireless network transmission within and around buildings with a view to encourage the development of telecom-ready and telecom-compatible buildings and spaces. This work builds on the knowledge that most building materials, vegetation, the configuration/layout of a building and its contents or built environment and the position of base stations or receivers affect the human telecommunications experience within the built spaces. This paper also intends to emphasize the need for stakeholders especially regulatory bodies in the built environment to develop guidelines for telecom-ready / compatible buildings making use of the available data from research in the telecommunication field. The authors' intention is to strike up concern amongst built industry professionals towards answering the following salient questions:

- What guidelines / standard can be used in determining the rating of a built facility's overall performance with regards to wireless communication?
- What are the impacts of our local, common building materials on electromagnetic waves?
- What are impacts of building orientation, spatial configuration and sizes, site planning, on the quality of wireless communication in the environment?
- What standards and frameworks should be referenced by built environment professionals while designing buildings?

If we must achieve this all-important goal, we must focus research efforts towards;

- i. Determination and development of ideal guidelines / standard to be used in determining the rating of a built facility's overall performance with regards to wireless communication.
- ii. Determination of the positive and negative impact of our local, common building materials on electromagnetic waves and how to improve on them for optimum human and mechanical efficiency.
- iii. Determination of the impact of building orientation, spatial configuration and sizes, site planning, on the quality of wireless communication in the indoor environment.

- iv. Determination and development of standards and frameworks to be referenced by built environment professionals as well as the telecom industry while designing buildings and placing telecom infrastructure respectively.
- v. The inclusion in the national building code of standards derived from this study to guide future developments.

In northern cold countries, thick reinforced walls and energy efficient windows composed of several layers of glass plus metal coating are becoming the de facto elements in modern building constructions, and it has been noticed that they can impact heavily on radio signal propagation. Rodriguez et al (2014).

The tests he conducted show a material and frequency dependent attenuation, with an average increase of 20-25 dB in modern constructions compared to old construction, which presents a low and almost constant attenuation below 10 dB. The different results and observations presented along the paper are useful for future radio network and built environment planning considerations.

The hypothetical stance for this work therefore is set down on the knowledge that the spatial configuration and materials that Architects specify for use in their buildings substantially affects the quality of wireless reception and transmission (propagation) within and around those spaces and thus invariably bears significance on the human telecommunication experience of the spaces. It would therefore be safe to posit that with better informed and correct design, the use of appropriate building materials, and with proper spatial configuration/design, optimal performance of macro and micro wireless devices can be achieved and by extension, the human experience while using technological gadgets within and around such built spaces improved.

The quest for sustainability in the use of resources has affected every facet of human endeavor. If today, and increasingly so tomorrow, the major part of our lives and existence would depend greatly on wireless connectivity, whether in transit, at home, work or at the worship center, then there is very great need to understand the dynamics of the relationship between our design decisions on the built environment and the optimal performance settings for wireless telecommunication when used within those environments. This would indeed be akin to a kind of “tele-ergonomics”, where buildings are fashioned out for the ease of use and consumption of the end user.

Results of this would ultimately eradicate the above mentioned problems as well as furnish diverse practitioners and professionals in the built environment with guidelines they need in making the right and optimal design decisions.

Network service providers on the other hand, would through such study and research discover ways and manners to optimize their services at minimal cost and risks to human health.

Review of Related Literature

Wireless communication is one of the most important modes of transmission of information from one device to another. This work is focused toward wireless connectivity within the commercially used bandwidths (from 800 Mhz to 2400 Mhz) available for the following services: 2G capabilities GSM 900, and GSM 1800 3G capabilities UMTS 2100. 4G capabilities LTE 700, LTE 800, LTE 900, LTE 1800, LTE 2300 deployed within Nigeria.

This paper focuses on the interaction between the provision of 2G, 3G, and 4G wireless telecommunication services (Global System for Mobile Communication GSM network provision operating on the 800-2400 MHz spectrum as provided by MTN Nigeria, Airtel, Globacom, and Etisalat) and the usual built environment scenarios found in Nigeria.

This work is essentially delimited to Radio waves over small or large geographic areas which include Personal Area Networks (PANs), Local Area Networks (LANs), Metropolitan Area Networks (MANs), Large networks connecting states and countries called Wide Area Networks (WANs). It assumes that buildings are designed and constructed after these networks have been mounted / installed and not before and thus should be done in consideration of above mentioned elements.

Fig. 2: Wireless Distribution of Wireless Networks to Different Buildings. Source: Matrix IT

Figure 2 above explains pictorially, how the wireless technology spreads and communicates across neighboring buildings. In this technology, the information can be transmitted through the air without requiring any cable or wires or other electronic conductors, by using electromagnetic waves. In this present day, the wireless communication technology refers to a variety of wireless communication devices and technologies ranging from smart phones to computers, tabs, laptops, Bluetooth Technology, printers.

Over the past decade, the market for wireless service in Nigeria has grown at an unprecedented rate. The industry has expanded from cellular phones and pagers to Personal Communication Systems (PCS), wireless local area networks (WLANs), and broadband wireless services that can provide voice, data, and full-motion video in real time. While the earlier communication models or systems, though each short-lived, demanded that deliberate adjustments be made in the planning and building of our environment to accommodate its peculiarities, the same cannot be said of this most modern mode of communication, whose chief medium of disseminating information, electromagnetic waves, have been found not to perform optimally under certain physical conditions coupled with

the well-known health risks suspected to be associated with it. There has been absolutely no innovation geared towards ameliorating this growing problem.

Issues like path loss (unobstructed attenuation), attenuation, shadowing, diffraction and reflection amongst a few must be thoroughly understood for all concerned professionals in both the building and telecom industries to continue to function effectively.

Path loss is the reduction in power density of an electromagnetic wave as it propagates through space. This is influenced by terrain contours, environment (urban or rural, vegetation and foliage), propagation medium (dry or moist air), the distance between the transmitter and the receiver, and the height and location of antennas. These phenomena have been studied quite extensively in more advanced climes. Adopting there study verbatim here would be most ineffective as the conditions of our built environment: methods, spatial organization, development control, materials are substantially different.

It is common knowledge that certain types of building materials, the orientation of our buildings, positioning of interior or exterior telecommunication infrastructure, spatial configuration, size of our spaces and even the equipment we use all affect the performance of almost all of these wireless based tools. The extent and nature of these interactions with regards to our local peculiarities are not yet exhaustively understood and scientifically documented. The level of the electromagnetic fields depends on many factors, like the structure and topology of the house (for example the proportion of used area and wall structure),the environment, the building structure which surrounds us, the placement of electrical wires in the walls, the distance from the transmission tower in case of mobile communication, etc. (Vizi and Vandenbosch, 2016)

Construction practices and materials are currently changing, particularly in response to more demanding issues like energy efficiency requirements in light of the global move to 'zero carbon' status, other basic design considerations and requirements. There is however little awareness in the construction industry regarding the impact of design decisions on wireless coverage and the potential choices that may need to be met. Equally, there are no innovative products specifically aimed at solving this already existent problem. Awareness needs to be created in the construction industry about this issue and a discuss started about the implications for the much touted connected /smart home agenda (amongst other reasons) which are likely to require the increased use of wireless products to achieve effective management, as well as addressing other industries such as communications, tele-health, and entertainment.

Currently, in Nigeria, no rule or guidelines founded on proper research on the peculiarities of the built environment in Nigeria and how it interacts either positively or negatively with the usually carelessly deployed telecom infrastructure exist yet. To achieve an optimized wireless system for an environment, accurate propagation characteristics of the components (spatial, material, orientation, e.t.c) of the environment should be known. Inversely, built environment professionals ought to, on their part, understand the current status and long-term plan of telecom provision in the area they propose to develop in other to be better informed in making design decisions. This can only be achieved by thorough in-depth knowledge of the relationship between the components/sub-components of the built environment and the telecom wireless industry. The aim is to get a better understanding of the impact of modern buildings on the current and potential future technology and frequency bands used by cellular technologies. Knowing the electromagnetic characteristics of building materials, attenuation through walls and electromagnetic fields inside entire buildings can be simulated using computer programs. (Vizi and Vandenbosch, 2016).

From the literature review and the personal experience of the authors, it has been found that the Nigerian construction industry does not currently take into account the requirements of wireless signals, as they consider thermal, sound insulation /enhancement and such more important. This apparent lack of attention to the increased attenuation of

modern building materials could present a problem for cellular indoor coverage in the future. To model our buildings for efficient indoor wireless access or restriction is especially difficult because the channel characteristics vary widely according to the environment.

Furthermore, one has to understand the electromagnetic properties of building materials in order to evaluate their reflection and transmission coefficients, which constitute the RF (reflection and transmission) loss.

Armed with these values, we can take steps to effectively calculate and simulate how to shield our room or building, so that external electromagnetic fields will be reduced inside to a required level or do otherwise as the case often requires. The radio wave channel for indoors depends heavily on factors such as structure, layout of rooms, interior design /configuration and the type of construction materials used. (Stein, 1998)

Radiowave Propagation and the Environment

Effects of Building Materials On Radiowave Propagation

Radiowaves impinging on a building will enter the building by numerous mechanisms. The influence of the electrical properties of building materials on each mechanism is different. Material properties have a dominant effect on the reflection from, and transmission of, radiowaves through building materials and on the absorption of radiowave energy in those materials. These effects give rise to attenuation of the signal.

Fig 3: Indoor Radio Wave Propagation Modelling. Source: Symmetry

Other mechanisms include diffraction from the edges of materials and scatter from rough surfaces. This does not infer that the mechanisms are insignificant. In particular, diffraction can be the dominant propagation mechanism by which radio signals reach a receiver location.

Every (building) material has its own electromagnetic properties, just as it has for example mechanical and thermal conductivity properties. The electromagnetic properties to be considered are the permisivity (or dielectric constant), electric conductivity, and magnetic permeability. These constitutive characteristics are needed for example to determine reflection and transmission loss through a wall. In general they are frequency dependent. (Vizi and Vandenbosch, 2016).

The ability to treat propagation mechanisms such as reflection separately from diffraction and scatter arises from the fact that building elements such as walls, windows and doors are generally quasi-two-dimensional structures with sharply defined edges and

faces that are planar and smooth on the scale of a wavelength. Whilst this is only roughly true, and is frequency-dependent, all detailed computational models for propagation into and within buildings make these assumptions.

In order for the visions of 3rd and 4th generation of wireless communication standards to be realized, system design Engineers and the built environment professionals must have a thorough understanding of the wireless channels in which these devices operate. The main objective is to understand the effects of varied environmental factors on electromagnetic wave propagation and have more precise and flexible path-loss prediction model for indoor/outdoor wireless propagation.

Effect of Buildings on Radiowave Propagation

Here the small-scale details of construction materials and the physical mechanism by which electromagnetic waves penetrate buildings are largely ignored in favor of a statistical characterization of the bulk effect. The cumulative effect of all building materials used and their spatial peculiarities have been found to affect in no small measure the nature of the radio propagation for users within the building. Rudd et al (2014).

Fig 4: Showing Wireless Propagation across a City. Source: REMCOM

Figure 4 above shows the nature of wireless network propagation across a typical city. Propagation tools require site-specific information for the particular environment. In urban microcellular scenarios, the received signal is composed of energy reflected, transmitted, or diffracted by buildings. Additional signals, scattered from trees, lamps, telephone boxes, etc., can be neglected. Therefore, data required for the propagation models consist of the geometrical and electrical characteristics of buildings in the microcell. Rappaport et al, (1993).

Effects of Foliage, House Shadowing, *TR (Transmission, receiver) Separation, Receiver Height and External Features on Radio Propagation

In experiments reported, the results of path loss and building penetration loss measurements in residential areas and homes were made. Detailed measurements were performed in the 5.85 GHz NII band for three typical middle- to upper-middleclass houses and for deciduous and coniferous stands of trees.

Fig 5: Multi-Path and Direct Path Propagation. Source: Science direct

Figure 5 above shows in a pictorial form the different possible methods of wireless network propagation and how reflection occurs when they interact. Specific effects of foliage, house shadowing, TR separation, and receiver height were quantified for outdoor path loss in residential areas. The same study also determined how exterior shadowing, house construction, and floor plan arrangement influence the penetration of radio waves into homes. Results show that, at 5.85 GHz, home penetration attenuates signals at an average of 14 dB, tree shadowing attenuates signals between 11 and 16 dB, and close-in house shadowing attenuates signals between 15 and 21 dB, depending on the height of the receive antenna, Durgin et al (1998). Though the frequencies are different from those in popular use here, substantial inferences can be safely modelled from these studies.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Fig 6: Workflow for Adoption & Implementation of Effective Design Strategies for Telecom-Compatible Built Environments. Source: Authors.

Figure 6 above summarizes the steps or structure that can be applied to achieve meaningful gains with regards to optimizing our built environment for telecommunication use.

The authors of this paper have made an attempt to turn the spot light on a rather little known aspect of building planning and development which has to do with the production of telecom-compatible buildings.

The design and development of telecom compatible buildings, bothers on the ability to compensate for the dynamics of radio propagation within the built environment. One cannot provide for what he does not fully understand. Thus, the call is on for an improved awareness on the part of Architects and other concerned professionals on the subject with a view to enhancing human experience within the spaces we provide for them.

This paper has fundamentally argued that the availability and thus propagation of the wireless means of data communication has come to stay and therefore should be a factor when we design buildings. Any attempt to undermine this fact, would invariably result in a less than desirable environmental outcome.

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